

ANALYSIS OF SMART HELMETS AND DESIGNING AN IOT BASED SMART HELMET: A COSTEFFECTIVE SOLUTION FOR RIDERS

Nenavath Shireesha¹, Suragoni Rakesh Goud²,

Pathlavath Redya Naik³, Ms. V. Sumathi⁴

^{1,2,3} UG Student, Dept. of ECE, CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

⁴ Assistant Professor, Dept. of ECE,
CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

ABSTARCT:

In this paper, we have reviewed the recent trends in developing Smart Helmet system. The smart helmet system is used to prevent the accidents in motor bikes and to identify the bike accidents on time for wellness of human being. Also, the smart helmet system analyzed in this paper is used in mining industry for safeguarding the miners from hazardous events in the mine and to alert the miners from hazardous gas emissions inside it. The research also helps to understand the smart helmet system evolved over the period and currently by using emerging technology like Internet of Things (IoT). This work also addresses the intelligent motor bike helmet system which is used to inform the rider about rear big trucks/buses for avoiding collisions.

INTRODUCTION

In every aspect of our life safety and security are the major important areas. Now-a-days the scenario that we come across in many cases of human deaths and

severe injuries to people is because of two-wheeler road accidents. And it is a crucial issue that requires everybody's attention, for every four minutes there is one death being reported in India. As per World Health Organization (WHO) we have identified that 40% of the deaths and 70% of severe injuries can be reduced if bike rider wears the helmet [1].

Fig. 1 Indian road accident safety report

Now a day's wearing helmet is compulsory for every two wheeler riders and also it is equally important for pillion riders too to wear the helmet, but the discomfort or inconvenience caused due to wearing conventional helmet makes the rider to avoid using the helmet and finally it leads to death of the rider. In spite of the fact that helmets are being available to everybody, people are just not wearing them and the

main reason behind it is that the conventional helmets are generating unconditional temperatures inside it which makes inconvenience to the person. Currently in the existing system, when the person met with an accident we are not in a position to ensure the immediate first aid treatment; due to this late medication the person may die. With the help of proposed system in this paper, it triggers an automatic alert message to the concerned person or to the ambulance in case of any emergency situation like an accident. The alert message consists of the details such as location of the accident and time of accident, which will help to speed up the first aid service to the casualty. The Internet of Things (IoT) can provide an infrastructure which integrates the smart services with situational responses, and also allows mutual communication between smart things or devices and people over a network. So we have come up with this idea of IoT based smart helmet which ensures the safety of the rider while riding. The idea of proposing this system has mainly come from the social responsibility towards the society. The proposed system allows the rider to start a bike only on wearing the helmet. This system will not allow driver to ride if he had consumed alcohol. This system identifies the bike accidents with accuracy and gives information to the nearby hospital and relatives of the rider

who met with an accident. It also tracks the location details of the rider and alcohol consumption of the rider and will be stored in the cloud/server

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the process of literature survey, we have found a lot of smart helmets with different approaches and with different methodologies.

C. J. Behr et al [2] had proposed a smart helmet for mining industry in order to identify hazardous event detection and air quality. This system can identify the concentration level of the harmful gases such as CO, SO₂, NO₂, and particulate matter by using electro chemical sensor and also detects the removal of Helmet by using an IR sensor. It also identifies an incident when miners are struck by an object in contradiction to their head with a high force exceeding a value of 1000 by using the Head Injury Criteria. An accelerometer was used to calculate the acceleration of the head after hit and the HIC was calculated in software.

Edna Elizabeth et al [3] had developed a smart helmet device for detecting and reporting bike accidents. Smart helmet system comprises of various sensors, and it identify the accident by evaluating uneven or irregular variations obtained from sensor system, and a trigger will be sent to Pager

Duty from the microcontroller. Pager Duty will then triggers a call to the phone number registered by the motorist. If the driver does not respond to it for a period of 5 minutes after the first call is initiated, then the emergency contacts will be informed with the details about the accident. The emergency contacts will be alerted through text message, e-mail, and phone call until they acknowledge the incident. In real time, this system assures a reliable and quick delivery of information relating to the accident.

Rashmi Vashisth et al [4] had proposed a methodology which uses Piezo electric buzzer in order to identify over speeding bike and it also equipped with a feature called velocity limiter, which restricts the speed limit of the bike. It also has a feature which prevents the drunk and drive scenarios of the rider called as ALCHO-LOCK and an accelerometer to identify accidents, upon detecting accidents it automatically send a message to concerned person. A fog sensor has been used in this system in order to improve the visibility for the rider in case of fog or smog. It also features automatic deduction of required or needed amount from the riders registered virtual wallet in wireless to helps the rider to stop and do the payment.

Selvathi et al [5] had designed a system which automatically detects if the rider is

wearing a helmet and also checks whether the rider has consumed alcohol before starting the ride. The relay attached to the engine will turn ON if and only if both the conditions are met. The Microcontroller in the system controls the functioning of relay and thus the ignition. This system also identifies the bike accident at any place and alerts the concerned person about the accident.

EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing system has a wireless telecommunication and the system is connected to a smart phone. The prototype uses sensors to detect a crash or accidents and the communication hardware is used to automatically dial a predefined emergency contact. The other existing system has a sensor which is used to control the speed of the vehicle. The helmet is fixed with all the components and sensors that read the status of the bike rider and accordingly instructs the rider to reduce or increase the speed based on the sensor value. Along with the speed limit sensors, the helmet also checks if the rider is drunk. If the rider is drunk then the ignition of the bike is avoided and hence the rider is not allowed to ride the bike.

DISADVANTAGES

- System with high cost and high complexity.
- Need of Traffic Policemen.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

TRANSMITTER:

Fig: Block Diagram of SMART HELMET Transmitter Section

RF TRANSMITTER

The STT-433 is ideal for remote control applications where low cost and longer range is required. The transmitter operates from a 1.5-12V supply, making it ideal for battery-powered applications. The transmitter employs a SAW-stabilized oscillator, ensuring accurate frequency control for best range performance. Output power and harmonic emissions are easy to control, making FCC and ETSI compliance easy. The manufacturing-friendly SIP style package and low-cost make the STT-433 suitable for high volume applications.

RECEIVER SECTION:

Fig: Block Diagram of Smart Helmet Receiver Section

SAW stabilized oscillator

The transmitter is basically a negative resistance LC oscillator whose center frequency is tightly controlled by a SAW resonator. SAW (Surface Acoustic Wave) resonators are fundamental frequency devices that resonate at frequencies much higher than crystals.

RF RECEIVER

The STR-433 is ideal for short-range remote control applications where cost is a primary concern. The receiver module requires no external RF components except for the antenna. It generates virtually no emissions, making FCC and ETSI approvals easy. The super-regenerative design exhibits exceptional sensitivity at a very low cost. The manufacturing-friendly SIP style package and low-cost make the STR-433 suitable for high volume applications.

CONCLUSION

Currently we are in the process of finding an appropriate design for the helmet. The proposed helmet should accommodate all the needed facilities in a compact manner. In parallel, the selection of microcontroller and sensors are being taken care. The proposed design will give a solution in terms of cost effective and updated technology front for all kinds of helmets. The aim is to target the two wheelers segment and then bi cycle users with lighter version. This cost effective solution can be integrated with engine start and other needed safety aspects.

REFERENCES

- [1] Prudhvi Raj R, Sri Krishna Kanth, BhargavAdityaBharath K, (2014) “Smart-tec Helmet” Electrical and Electronics Engineering, GITAM University,Rushikonda, Visakhapatnam, India. Advance in Electronic and Electric Engineering 4: 493-498.
- [2] Behr, C.J., Kumar, A., Hancke, G.P “ A Smart Helmet for Air Quality and Hazardous Event Detection for the Mining Industry” Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Industrial Technology 2016- May,7475079, pp. 2026-2031
- [3] Sreenithy Chandran, Sneha Chandrasekar, N Edna Elizabeth “Konnnect: An Internet of Things(IoT) based smart

helmet for accident detection and notification” 2016 IEEE Annual India Conference (INDICON)

[4] Rashmi Vashisth, Sanchit Gupta, Aditya Jain, Sarthak Gupta, Sahil, Prashant Rana “Implementation and analysis of smart helmet” 2017 4th International Conference on Signal Processing, Computing and Control (ISPCC)

[5] D. Selvathi, P. Pavithra, T. Preethi “Intelligent Transportation System for Accident Prevention and Detection” 2017 International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS)

[6] Archana D, Boomija G, Manisha J, Kalaiselvi V. K. G. “Mission On! Innovations in Bike Systems to Provide a Safe Ride Based on IOT ” 2017 2nd International Conference on Computing and Communications Technologies (ICCCT)

[7] Sayan Tapadar, Shinjini Ray; Himadri, Nath Saha; Arnab, Kumar Saha, Robin Karlose “ Accident and alcohol detection in bluetooth enabled smart helmets for motorbikes” 2018 IEEE 8th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)

[8] Radha Krishna Karne and Dr. T. K. Sreeja (2022), A Novel Approach for Dynamic Stable Clustering in VANET Using Deep Learning (LSTM) Model. IJEER 10(4), 1092-1098. DOI: 10.37391/IJEER.100454.

[9] Reddy, Kallem Niranjana, and Pappu Venkata Yasoda Jayasree. "Low Power Strain and Dimension Aware SRAM Cell Design Using a New Tunnel FET and Domino Independent Logic." *International Journal of Intelligent Engineering & Systems* 11, no. 4 (2018).

[10] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Design of a Dual Doping Less Double Gate Tfet and Its Material Optimization Analysis on a 6t Sram Cells."

[11] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Low power process, voltage, and temperature (PVT) variations aware improved tunnel FET on 6T SRAM cells." *Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems* 21 (2019): 143-153.

[12] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Survey on improvement of PVT aware variations in tunnel FET on SRAM cells." In *2017 International Conference on Current Trends in Computer, Electrical, Electronics and Communication (CTCEEC)*, pp. 703-705. IEEE, 2017

[13] Karne, R. K. ., & Sreeja, T. K. . (2023). PMLC- Predictions of Mobility and Transmission in a Lane-Based Cluster VANET Validated on Machine Learning. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 11(5s), 477–483. <https://doi.org/10.17762/ijritcc.v11i5s.7109>